

Learning Probabilistic Graph Models to Prevent Device Failure in Managed Services

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INTRODUCTION:

While the concept of predictive maintenance (PdM) has been around for years, only now can it be realized to its full potential due to the recent progress in IoT technologies. Large amounts of data from networks of interconnected sensors and other distributed devices are used to predict imminent failure and proactively deploy service. PdM is predominantly used in manufacturing and structural engineering industries. This study explores PdM applications in managed service business models such as MPS or DaaS.

AIM:

In this study, we are simultaneously addressing two business problems that are ubiquitous to managed services. The client-centric problem is to ensure business continuity by preventing system failure, downtime or suboptimal performance. The service provider, on the other hand, is interested in savings costs by decreasing the number of service calls, improving maintenance efficiency and reducing component redundancy. To translate these problem statements into the language of data science, we are required to learn a scalable, self-updating real-time predictive model which would alert the service provider of an impending change in the system state.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Several real-life raw datasets were used to learn and test Bayesian Networks (BN) and Hidden Markov models (HMM). We use R to develop model prototypes and Microsoft Azure to experiment with model scalability.

RESULTS:

There are numerous inherent uncertainties associated with mining sensor and machine log data, such as, intermittent missing data and sensor read-out errors, delayed system response, the presence of non-random-independent variables, and the general lack of ground truth labels for meaningful supervised learning. Thus, most deterministic models fail to produce reliable predictions. Bayesian networks, on the other hand, are capable of handling all or most of these uncertainty factors. We trained a number of BN models using several different learning approaches and compared their performance and applicability within particular business settings. For example, while many previous studies rely on dynamic BN to handle temporal data, we will show that time-to-event models are in fact a better alternative which results in more compact and less overfitting graphs. The choice of the starting-point graph for BN learning is another powerful differentiator which is to be discussed in detail. Should we start from a graph reflecting the current understanding of the causal relationships in the system? We will show that learning

from scratch with multiple restarts often reveals previously unknown causes of system failure. Finally, we will discuss the tradeoffs between model accuracy and scalability.

CONCLUSIONS:

We developed a model for predictive maintenance in managed services capable of alerting stakeholders of impending system component failure and contributing to subject matter expertise by revealing previously unknown inter-component relationship and causes of failure.

KEYWORDS:

Probabilistic graphical models, Predictive maintenance; Bayesian networks; Hidden Markov model; IIoT; Industry 4.0; Managed services; Self-learning

BIOGRAPHY:

Vlad has a Ph.D. and B. Sc. in materials engineering, M.Sc. in experimental physics, and 17 years of experience in industrial R&D. He is a co-inventor of 51 US Patents. After many years in scientific research at the frontiers between experimental science and complex system engineering, he now applies scientific principles and data science methodologies to solving complex business problems.